

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 3.2

NERD API: source code, open source licensing and documentation

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Contents

I. Abstract of the short report (M6)	3
II. Links	3
A. Source code	3
B. Licensing	3
C. Documentation	3

I. Abstract of the short report (M6)

In M3 were released the technical specifications. The document provides an overview of the tool and describes how to interact through its REST API. Produced as documentation it's the reference document for the HIRMEOS partners.

The NERD technology is now released as an open source software.

The application is released under an Apache 2 licence. The code is hosted on a public GitHub repository, accessible by anybody and without any limitation.

The official documentation is a living resource allowing to follow the evolution of the tool. The platform used for hosting is readthedocs.com.

II. Links

A. Source code

<http://github.com/kermitt2/nerd>

B. Licensing

<https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>

C. Documentation

<http://nerd.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>